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Application of the hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams to predict necking in metal bellows forming process

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Abstract

In order to predict the initiation of necking in metal bellows forming process, a methodology for determination of the Forming Limit Diagram (FLD) and the Forming Limit Stress Diagram (FLSD) is represented in this paper. The methodology is based on the Marciniak and Kuczynski (M-K) model. Comparison between the experimental and theoretical results for hydroforming stress and strain limit diagrams as predicted by different methods indicates that the present approach is suitable for prediction of necking in tube hydroforming processes. Afterwards, the implementation of the hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams into finite element numerical simulations for the forming of the metal bellows is established. A satisfactory agreement between the finite element method (FEM) and test results is achieved.

Keywords: Metal bellows; Hydroforming stress limit diagram; FEM; Experiment.

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1. Introduction

Metal bellows are cylindrical vessels that can be compressed when pressure is used on the top or the bottom of the vessel (or both). When the pressure is removed, the bellow will return back to its original shape. Metal bellows have wide applications in aerospace, micro-electromechanical and industrial systems. Numerous papers have dealt with various aspects of bellows except for analyzing the forming process.

Igi et al. [1] reported the use of the bellows as the element of expansion joint in various piping systems. Bellows have the function to absorb regular or irregular expansion and contraction in such piping systems. Lee [2] carried out parametric study on some of the forming process parameters of the metal bellows by FE. A finite element analysis technique is applied to the tube-bulging and folding processes as well as the springback stage. Kang et al. [3] mentioned that tubular bellows are one of the most efficient energy-absorbing elements for various automotive systems. It is also mentioned that, in general, the manufacturing of metal bellows consists of a four-step process: (1) deep drawing, (2) ironing, (3) tube bulging, and (4) folding. Faraji et al. [4] presented a new method for manufacturing of the metal bellows and important parameters such as initial length of tube, internal pressure, axial feeding and velocity, mechanical properties and the type of materials were investigated by FE analysis and experimental tests. The explicit time integration method was used for modeling the tube-bulging and folding processes. Meanwhile, the implicit time integration method was used for the spring back stage. Finally, the results of FEM were compared with experiments and a very good agreement was found between them.

It is found in the literature that the stress-based FLD (FLSD) is much less sensitive to the strain path effect than the FLD. Thus, the FLSD can be used well for all forming

processes without concerning for strain path effects [5-9]. However, the FLD and FLSD are two mathematically equivalent representations of sheet metal or tube material forming limits in strain and stress spaces. As it is indicated in reference [10], the FLSD is much more favorable than the FLD in representing forming limits in the numerical simulation of multi-stage forming processes. The FLD concept allows a correct analysis on the material formability, while the FLSD concept means a good stop test on the applications involving non-proportional loading due to its characteristics [11]. Therefore, a combination of forming limit diagram and forming limit stress diagram can be used as a perfect approach in order to analyze material formability under multi-stage operations. Zimniak [12] presented the implementation of the forming limit diagrams determined by perturbation theory in FEM simulations. The computed strain distribution is compared directly with the theoretical forming limit diagrams and forming limit stress diagrams. An application of the theory is presented for sheet metal forming processes: an L-shape sheet forming, the deep drawing of a square cup, and the deep drawing of axisymmetric cups. The performed experimental verification of this theory is shown that the agreement between theory and experiment is good. Chen et al., [13] showed the application of the forming limit stress diagram for multi-step forming of auto panels.

Since bursting in hydroforming processes is the consequence of necking, the ability to predict necking is an important issue before designing the details of the processes [14]. Xing and Makinouchi [15] applied the diffuse necking criterion to the hydroforming process. An analytical approach for prediction of bursting as well as for buckling instability as the same time was presented by Tirosh et al. [16] and Xia [17]. Nefussi and Combescure [18] discussed Swift's two criteria for sheet forming and for tube hydroforming by supposing that necking and buckling occur simultaneously. Asnafi

[19] constructed the analytical models to show what the limits are during the free forming, how different material and process parameters influence the loading path and the forming result, and what an experimental investigation into hydroforming should focus on. An analytical approach for prediction of forming limits (both in strain and stress spaces) in tube hydroforming under combined internal pressure and independent axial feeding was discussed by Kim et al. [20, 21]. Kim and his co-workers used diffuse plastic instability based on the Hill's quadratic plastic potential to predict the initiation of necking. Finally, the hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams obtained from the above approach were verified with experimental results. Kim et al. [20] also investigated the influence of the plastic anisotropy on plastic instability, the limit stress and the bursting pressure. In addition, in order to predict fracture initiation, Oyanes's ductile fracture criterion was introduced and evaluated from the histories of stress and strain calculated by means of FE analysis [21]. Kim et al. [22] also developed the theoretical FLSD based on the local necking criterion to predict bursting failure in tube hydroforming processes. And then finite element analyses were carried out to find out the state of stresses and strains during the hydroforming operation, in which FLSD was utilized as forming limit criterion for assessing the onset of necking. Finally, the proposed analytical approach based on the implementation of the FLSD was verified with a series of bulge tests for three different load cases and showed a good agreement with the experimental results. In addition, the influences of material properties on bursting pressure are investigated using this approach. In these references [20-22], the tube was assumed to be thin enough for the plane stress hypothesis to be valid.

Most theoretical and numerical FLD or FLSD analyses were based on the well-known M-K model, presented by Marciniak and Kuczynski [23]. The basic assumption of this model was the existence of a material imperfection, in the form of a groove on the

surface of the sheet. They showed that a slight intrinsic inhomogeneity in load bearing capacity throughout a deformation sheet could lead to unstable growth of strain in the region of imperfection, and subsequently caused localized necking and failure. In the literature, there were many works which used M-K approach to determine sheet metal forming limits and the influence of various parameters on FLD or FLSD was investigated [11, 24-29]. However, few papers have studied forming process of the metal bellows, especially in hydroforming stage considering M-K approach in order to predict the initiation of necking.

In this paper, in order to predict the initiation of necking in metal bellows forming process, the M-K model was applied for prediction of hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams. The complete system of equations including four variables was considered. The modified Newton-Raphson method was applied to solve the nonlinear system of equations. The predicted forming limits both in strain and stress spaces were compared with published experimental and theoretical hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams respectively [20, 21, 30]. Afterwards, the implementation of the forming limit strain and stress diagrams for Phosphor Bronze Cusn6 bellows material into finite element numerical simulations for forming of the metal bellows was established by using a commercial code (ABAQUS/Explicit). The results obtained from the FEM showed very good agreements with the experimental data. Consequently, it was shown that the present approach for necking prediction proposed in this paper will provide a feasible method to satisfy the increasing practical demands for the computer-aided formability system for complex forming process, especially in metal bellows forming process.

2. Methodology of hydroforming strain and stress limits computation

In this work, the so-called M-K approach was applied to determine the hydroforming stress and strain limit diagrams. The schematic of M-K model is shown in Figure 1.

In this model, it was assumed that there was a shallow groove on material surface which caused the localized necking. The initial imperfection factor of the groove f_0 was defined as the material thickness ratio $f_0 = t_b/t_a$, where "t" denoted the thickness and subscript "0" denoted the initial state. This initial inhomogeneity grew continuously with plastic straining to eventually form a localized neck. Groove zone was called "b" and safe zone was named "a". The safe zone was subjected to proportional strains. It was also assumed that strains at groove direction in two regions were equal. In deformation process, strain ratio (minimum strain to maximum strain) outside the groove was constant. This ratio decreased in groove zone. In fact deformation in groove zone was close to plane strain. In practice, this type of groove could be caused by surface roughness or local thickness variation which could be formed before the process. Because of plane stress assumption, strain and stress increments in groove zone could directly be obtained with respect to the safe zone strain increments [9].

Computations of hydroforming limit strains and stresses were started with calculations of the stress and strain values in the safe zone. For this purpose, first a value was assumed for $\alpha = \sigma_2^a / \sigma_1^a$. The value of α remained constant at entire part of the computation process. At first, all strains were zero. The loading on the safe zone was started by considering a small value for $d\bar{\epsilon}^a$, ($d\bar{\epsilon}^a=0.0001$) and the equivalent strain, $\bar{\epsilon}^a$, was calculated. Then the effective stress \bar{s}_Y was obtained by hardening law. Since the effective stresses from hardening law and yield function must be equal, s_x^a

and s_y^a could be obtained. Using the assumed $d\bar{\varepsilon}^a$ in the flow rule, stress and strain components in the safe zone were easily calculated. Using the rotation matrix, \mathbf{T} , the strain and stress tensors were transformed to the groove system of coordinates:

$$\mathbf{s}^{ntz} = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{s}^{xyz} \mathbf{T}^T = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{nn}^s & s_{nt} \\ \varepsilon_{nt}^s & s_{tt} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

With,

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(q) & \sin(q) \\ \sin(q) & \cos(q) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

After calculating the stress and strain components in the safe zone, same variables must be calculated for the groove zone.

In order to obtain the stress and strain components in the groove zone (e.g., $\sigma_{nn}^b, \sigma_{tt}^b, \sigma_{nt}^b, d\varepsilon_{nn}^b, d\varepsilon_{tt}^b$ and $d\varepsilon_{nt}^b$), it was needed to have six equations, but based on this fact that strain increments are related together with the effective strain increment by the flow rule. The number of needed equations were reduced to four (e.g., $d\bar{\varepsilon}^b, \sigma_{nn}^b, \sigma_{tt}^b$ and σ_{nt}^b).

The system of equations consisted of equilibrium, compatibility and energy balance equations. The basic equations of the M-K model were related to equilibrium and compatibility conditions. The strain compatibility equation and force equilibrium equations could be considered by applying the boundary conditions at interface between the safe and groove region. The force equilibrium equations could be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{nt}^a &= F_{nt}^b \\ F_{nn}^a &= F_{nn}^b \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here F_{nn} and F_{nt} were forces in the normal and tangential directions in the groove. By introducing the stress state in these areas, equation 1 could be rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{nt}^a \exp(e_3^a) t_0^a &= s_{nt}^b \exp(e_3^b) t_0^b \\ s_{nn}^a \exp(e_3^a) t_0^a &= s_{nn}^b \exp(e_3^b) t_0^b \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where s_{nn} and s_{nt} were stress components in the “n” and “t” directions, t_0^a and t_0^b were initial material thicknesses in the safe and groove regions respectively. Imperfection factor f could be expressed as a function of the initial defect:

$$f = f_0 \exp(e_3^b - e_3^a) \quad (5)$$

Herein f_0 was the initial imperfection factor and denoted by t_0^b / t_0^a , and e_3 was the strain in thickness direction calculated by incompressibility condition:

$$e_3 = -(e_1 + e_2) \quad (6)$$

Thus, the force equilibrium equations could be summarized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f s_{nn}^b &= s_{nn}^a \\ f s_{nt}^b &= s_{nt}^a \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The compatibility requirement assumed that the elongation in the neck band direction was equal in both regions as follows:

$$d e_{tt}^b = d e_{tt}^a \quad (8)$$

Finally, the energy relation could be introduced as an extra equation (the 4th equation) as the following [25]:

$$(d \varepsilon_{nn}^b \sigma_{nn}^b + d \varepsilon_{tt}^b \sigma_{tt}^b + d \varepsilon_{nt}^b \sigma_{nt}^b) - d \bar{\varepsilon}^b \bar{\sigma}_Y = 0 \quad (9)$$

Where, $\bar{\sigma}_Y$ was calculated from the hardening rule.

Totally, the four nonlinear equations could be summarized as follows:

$$F_1 = \frac{d \varepsilon_{nn}^b \sigma_{nn}^b + d \varepsilon_{tt}^b \sigma_{tt}^b + d \varepsilon_{nt}^b \sigma_{nt}^b}{d \bar{\varepsilon}^b \bar{\sigma}_Y} - 1 = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$F_2 = \frac{d\varepsilon_{tt}^b}{d\varepsilon_{tt}^a} - 1 = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$F_3 = f \frac{\sigma_{mn}^b}{\sigma_{mn}^a} - 1 = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$F_4 = f \frac{\sigma_{nt}^b}{\sigma_{nt}^a} - 1 = 0 \quad (13)$$

If the Vector of functions was denoted as $[F] = [F_1 \ F_2 \ F_3 \ F_4]^T$ and the variable matrix was $[X] = [\sigma_{mn}^b \ \sigma_{tt}^b \ \sigma_{nt}^b \ d\varepsilon^b]$, to compute this latter matrix the Modified Newton-Raphson method was applied.

$$[X]_{i+1} = [X]_i + [dX]_i \quad (14)$$

$$[dX]_i = -[J]_{ij}^{-1} [F]_j \quad (15)$$

Where, $[J]_{ij}$, the Jacobian matrix is written as:

$$[J]_{ij} = \left[\frac{\partial F_i}{\partial X_j} \right] \quad (16)$$

To guarantee the convergence of solution, a simple backtracking technique has been included in the Newton-Raphson method. Also for the purpose of rapid convergence the so-called ‘‘Armijo’’ condition has been used in this study. Readers could find more details or explanations about the numerical approach in reference [25, 31].

Localized necking was caused when the equivalent strain increment in the groove region became 10 times greater than that in the safe region. When localized necking was reached, limiting strains were documented. Computation of the limiting strains was repeated for different values of θ , the groove orientation, between 0 and 90°. Groove orientation was function of strain increments in the safe zone and was derived as follows [9]:

$$\tan(\theta + d\theta) = \exp\left[(1 - \rho)d\varepsilon_1^a\right] \tan(\theta) \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Where, } \rho = \frac{d\varepsilon_2^a}{d\varepsilon_1^a} \quad (18)$$

By solving the nonlinear system of equations (mentioned earlier consisting of the force equilibrium, compatibility and energy equations) all the strain and stress components in the safe and groove zone were obtained.

As mentioned earlier, computations of tube material limiting strains and stresses were repeated for different value of θ between 0 and 90°. Minimum value of major localization strain was selected among the calculation loops by variation of θ . The selected minimum strain and stress for any value of α were used in plotting of the FLD and FLSD, respectively.

3 Constitutive equations

The quadratic Hill's criterion (1948) and Holloman hardening law were applied to the plastic calculations of the experimental and theoretical hydroforming stress and strain limit diagrams.

3.1 Quadratic Hill's yield criterion

To take into account the effect of the anisotropy, the quadratic Hill's criterion was employed [32]. It is a generalization of the Von Mises criterion:

$$\bar{\sigma}_y^2 = \sigma_{xx}^2 - 2H\sigma_{xx}\sigma_{yy} + (F + H)\sigma_{yy}^2 + 2P\sigma_{xy}^2 \quad (19)$$

Where F, G, H and P could be calculated using the anisotropy coefficients r_0, r_{45} and r_{90} .

3.2 Hardening law description

Hardening law, namely Holloman law, was considered to describe the material work-hardening. Hollomon equation is given by

$$\bar{\sigma}_Y = K(\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon})^n \quad (20)$$

Where $\bar{\sigma}_Y$ denotes the effective stress, $\varepsilon_0, \bar{\varepsilon}$ are the pre-strain and the effective strain respectively, n is the strain hardening exponent and K is the strength constant.

4. Hydroforming stress and strain limit diagrams Verification

In order to evaluate the present approach proposed in this paper, the predicted FLD and FLSD were compared with the hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams obtained experimentally [20, 21] and the hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams determined theoretically from diffuse necking criterion which was presented by Kim et al. [20, 21]. In these references, a series of tube bulging tests were executed to evaluate the forming limit in hydroforming process. The mechanical properties of the tube material (STKM-11A tube) are shown in Table 1.

An internal hydraulic pressure has been used to bulge a tube that was supported between a lower and an upper die in these tests. The lower part of the tube was fixed in movement, while the other was free to be able to move in the downward direction. This condition could provide axial feeding during the test. During the hydroforming operation, only a limited amount of material could be fed into the die cavity. Thus, as applied internal pressure was increased, the thickness of material within the die cavity was reduced rapidly and consequently necking occurred. On the other hand, the compressive load applied at the ends of the material increased the amount of material inflow into the die cavity. Therefore, it prevented abrupt thinning of tube wall and could delay the onset of the necking. Readers can find the dimensions and configurations of

the die and final bulged part in reference [20]. For observing the bursting failure, high internal pressures under relatively low axial feeding as shown in Figure 2 were applied. Under the five load cases carried out in reference [20], the bursting failure had been occurred before the outer surface of the bulged tube reached inner wall of the die. Thus, it was reasonable that the experimental conditions could be considered to be in free forming process. The experimental data presented in the strain space. Therefore, they needed to be converted first into stress space. The process of the strain conversion was based on the method suggested by Stoughton [6]. Based on preceding discussion, in Figure 3, the verification of the present approach was performed. In addition, the predicted FLD and FLSD were also compared with experimental data from Asnafi and Skogsga°rdh [30] for further verification. The experimental data [30] had been obtained by tube hydroforming. The material was 1.47-mm thick hot-dip galvanized (HG:Z140) DP600. $t_0 = 1.47$ mm, $d_0 = 60$ mm and $L_0 = 220$ mm were the initial tube wall thickness, diameter and length, respectively. The mechanical properties of this material are shown in Table 1. This verification is shown in Figure 4.

The effect of imperfection factor, f_0 , on FLDs and FLSDs is an important issue in the M-K analysis [11, 25]. The level of the predicted FLD and FLSD rises when this factor increases. Thus, to obtain any particular FLD or FLSD the proper value of this factor must be first selected. For this purpose, the value of this factor is decreased from its highest value, i.e. 1, until good agreement is found between predicted and experimental FLD or FLSD values.

5. FE modeling

The manufactured bellows had 10 rings and the material was Phosphor Bronze CuSn6. Initial tube material properties and dimensions can be seen in table 2.

The forming process of the metal bellows was modeled and simulated using the ABAQUS-Explicit commercial finite element code. Due to the convergence problems encountered in implicit method in forming stages, an explicit method was used in bulging and folding stages. Elastic-plastic numerical formulation was used in FEM. Only one ring of the bellows was modeled, because of the symmetry. Totally 56 RAX2 axisymmetric type elements were used to mesh one ring of the bellows. Figure 5 shows annular rigid plate dies and deformable tube.

Dimensions and mechanical properties are shown in Figure 5 and Table 2, in which r_0 and t_0 are the initial radius, thickness of the tube, D_c is Die stroke (the initial distance between the plate dies) and d is plate dies thickness. The fillet radius is 0.5 mm. The coefficient of friction is 0.1 in FEM.

In this work, based on Faraji et al. [4] the metal bellows was formed in two stages (bulging and folding) from seamless full annealed tube. Loading conditions (axial displacement and internal pressure) are shown in Figure 6. In bulging and folding processes, the tube was constrained by some equally spaced annular plate dies. In the bulging step, internal pressure was increased linearly with time and no axial displacement was applied (0-0.005sec. in Figure 6). In the folding step, axial feeding was applied to the end of the tube, while internal pressure remained constant (0.005-0.01sec in Figure 6). During bulging, the length of the tube was constant and no axial displacement was applied. As soon as the internal pressure reached its maximum value at the end of the bulging step, folding stage was started and displacement was applied to the end of the tube and internal pressure remained constant.

6. Experimental procedure

The results of the finite element simulations were used for conducting the experiments. The die stroke in experiment was 10 mm, feeding 95% and internal pressure 4.5 MPa. The pressure was produced by a gear type pump, in which there was considerable fluctuation in pressure. Because of the sensitivity of the process to variation of internal pressure, using a system to eliminate these fluctuations was necessary. The fluid used in the experiment was a kind of mineral oil and one of the problems in the experiment was to seal the ends of the tube because the tube thickness was so thin. The annular plate die material was AISI420 stainless steel that was hardened to 45 HRC.

7. Results and discussions

Figure 7 (a) shows the hydroforming stress limit diagram and major and minor stress values extracted from FEM for bellows that modeled for an internal pressure 4.65 MPa and a die stroke equal to 10 mm. This figure shows that the resulted stress values from FEM are in safe region and Figure 7 (b) shows manufactured bellows according to the mentioned parameters that satisfy the analysis and FEM process. Figure 7 (c) shows FEM simulation of the part shown in Figure 7 (b) (e.g., acceptable part). Thus, the hydroforming stress limit diagram

Figure 8 (a) shows hydroforming stress limit diagram and major and minor stress values extracted from FEM for bellows modeled with an internal pressure 4.8 MPa and a die stroke equal to 10 mm. This figure shows that some of the resulted stress values from FEM are not in the safe region and failure may occur. Figure 8 (b) shows failure in the bellows manufactured according to the mentioned parameters that satisfy the analysis and FEM process. Figure 8 (c) shows the bellows failure and stress contours distribution.

Figure 9 shows hydroforming strain limit diagram and major and minor strains extracted from FEM for acceptable bellows that formed in internal pressure of 4.65 MPa. Based on this figure, necking (bursting) occurs in the manufactured bellows but the final bellows was actually manufactured soundly without any failure as shown in Figure 7 (b). E.g., for the element 400: the strain values were (-0.138, 0.235) and the corresponding stress values were (-45.878, 389.712). By comparing these two points with FLD and FLSD, respectively. We could find that the strain values were above the forming limit diagram but the corresponding stress values were below the forming limit stress diagram. This contradiction can be explained by considering the strain-path dependent nature of the FLD. It causes the method to become ineffective in the analysis of complex sheet metal forming processes, especially sheet and tube hydroforming. As mentioned earlier, the FLSD is much less sensitive to strain path effect than the FLD. Thus, the FLSD is a better criterion which can be implemented in FEM simulations in order to predict the initiation of necking in hydroforming process.

The strain path of element 428 during the process has been shown in Figure 10, in order to report more clearly, the strain path of the process related to figures 7 and 9 (to highlight and demonstrate the non-linearity of the strain path). Thus, one could see that the strain path was not linear.

Recently, Simha et al. [33] developed an extended stress-based forming limit diagram (XSFLD) that could be used to predict the onset of necking in sheet metal loaded under non-proportional load paths, as well as under three-dimensional stress states. The conventional strain-based FLD was transformed into the stress-based FLD advanced by Stoughton [6]. This, in turn, was converted into the XSFLD, which was characterized by the two invariants, mean stress and equivalent stress. Assuming that the stress states at the onset of necking under plane stress loading are equivalent to those under three-

dimensional loading, the XSFLD was used in conjunction with FE computations to predict the onset of necking during tubular hydroforming. In this study, the tube was assumed to be thin enough for the plane stress hypothesis to be valid. Thus, the present FLSD approach could be used as a criterion for necking prediction. Although it is easy to extend the present approach for determination of an extended stress-based forming limit diagram (XSFLD).

8. Conclusions

- A methodology already developed for prediction of the sheet metal forming limits has been extended and applied to determine the hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams.
- The methodology is based on the M-K model. The hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams computed by this method have been compared with published experimental and theoretical hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams for STKM-11A and DP600 (HG:Z140) tube material and good agreement has been observed.
- The FLD and FLSD for Phosphor Bronze CuSn6 bellows have been computed and implemented into FE simulations. The results obtained from the experiments show very good agreement with the results of finite element method.
- As mentioned earlier, the FLSD is much less sensitive to strain path effect than the FLD. Thus, the FLSD is a better criterion to predict the initiation of necking in hydroforming process.
- By using the present methodology for the prediction of hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams in the CAD/FEM, it is possible to make the design of metal

bellows forming processes much simpler and to eliminate expensive and time consuming trial-and-error techniques.

Appendix I: Notation

E	Young's elastic modulus
f	Imperfection factor
F_m, F_{nt}	Force equations in the groove directions
F, F_i	Functions vector and its component respectively
$K, n, m, \bar{\epsilon}_0$	Material constants
r	Average anisotropic parameter
r_0, r_{45}, r_{90}	Ratios of transverse to through-thickness strains under uniaxial tension at 0, 45 and 90° to the rolling direction
t	Material thickness
T	Rotation matrix
x, x_j	Variables vector and its component respectively
σ_1, σ_2	Stress components in the material coordinates
$\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{xy}$	Planer components of stress tensor in the orthotropic referential frame
$\sigma_{nm}, \sigma_{nt}, \sigma_{tt}$	Stress components in the groove coordinates in the state of plane stress
$\bar{\sigma}_Y$	Effective stress obtained from hardening law
$\bar{\sigma}_y$	Effective stress obtained from yield function

$\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}$	Rate of effective plastic strain
$\bar{\epsilon}$	Effective plastic strain
$d\bar{\epsilon}$	Effective plastic strain increment
$d\epsilon_1, d\epsilon_2, d\epsilon_3$	Strain increments in the material coordinates
$d\epsilon_{tt}, d\epsilon_{mm}, d\epsilon_{nt}$	Strain increments in the groove coordinates
$d\epsilon$	Strain increments tensor
ν	Poisson's ratio
α	Ratio of stresses along the strain path
ρ	Ratio of strain increments along the strain path
θ	Groove angle between the groove coordinates and the material coordinates

References

- [1] Igi Satoshi, katayama Hiroshi, kawahara Masanori (2000) Evaluation of mechanical behavior of new type bellows with two directional convolutions. *Nuclear engineering & design* 197(1-2): 107-114.
- [2] Lee S.W. (2002) Study on the forming parameters of the metal bellows. *J. Mater. Proc. Tech.* 130-131: 47-53.
- [3] Kang Boo Hyun, Lee Moon Yong, Shon Sung Man, Moon Young Hoon (2007) Forming various shapes of tubular bellows using a single-step hydroforming process. *J. Mater. Proc. Tech.* 194 (1-3): 1–6.
- [4] Faraji Gh., Mosavi Mashhadi M., Norouzifard V. (2008). Evaluation of effective parameters in metal bellows forming process. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. Doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2008.07.057 (in press).
- [5] Arrieux R., Bedrin C., Bovin M. (1982) Determination of an intrinsic forming limit stress diagram for isotropic sheets. In: *Proceedings of the 12th IDDRG congress, Santa Margherita, Ligure. 2*, pp. 61-71.
- [6] Stoughton T. B. (2000) A general forming limit criterion for sheet metal forming, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 42 (1): 1–27.
- [7] Stoughton T.B., Zhu X. (2004) Review of theoretical models of the strain-based FLD and their relevance to the stress-based FLD. *Int. J. Plasticity*, 20 (8-9): 1463–1486.

- [8] Hashemi R. (2007) Consideration of path effects on prediction of forming limit diagrams, M.S. Thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sharif University of Technology.
- [9] Assempour A., Hashemi R., Abrinia K., Ganjiani M., Masoumi E., 2009. A methodology for prediction of forming limit stress diagrams considering the strain path effect. *Computational Materials Science*, 45 (2): 195-204.
- [10] Wu P.D., Graf A., MacEwen S.R., Lloyd D.J., Jain M., Neale K.W. (2005) On forming limit stress diagram analysis, *Int. J. Solids and Struct.* 42 (8): 2225-2241.
- [11] Butuc M.C., Gracio J.J., Barata da Rocha A. (2006) An experimental and theoretical analysis on the application of stress-based forming limit criterion, *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*. 48 (4): 414-429.
- [12] Zimniak Z. (2000) Implementation of the forming limit stress diagram in FEM simulations, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 106 (1-3): 261-266.
- [13] Chen M.H., Gao L., Zuo D.W., Wang M. (2007) Application of the forming limit stress diagram to forming limit prediction for multi-step forming of auto panels, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. 187-188: 173-177.
- [14] Kim J., Kim Y. W., Kang B. S., Hwan S. M. (2004) Finite element analysis for bursting failure prediction in bulge forming of a seamed tube, *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, 40: 953–966.
- [15] Xing HL, Makinouchi A. (2001) Numerical analysis and design for tubular hydroforming, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 43 (4): 1009–1026.
- [16] Tirosh J., Neuberger A., Shirizly A. (1996) On tube expansion by internal fluid pressure with additional compressive stress, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 38: 839–851.
- [17] Xia Z. C. (2001) Failure analysis of tubular hydroforming. *J. Eng. Mater. Techno.* 123: 423–429.

- [18] Nefussi G., Combescure A. (2002) Coupled buckling and plastic instability for tube hydroforming. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*. 44 (5): 899–914.
- [19] Asnafi N. (1999) Analytical modelling of tube hydroforming, *Thin-Walled Structures*, 34: 295–330.
- [20] Kim J., Kim S. W., Song W. J., Kang B. S. (2004) Analytical approach to bursting in tube hydroforming using diffuse plastic instability. *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 46 (10): 1535–1547.
- [21] Kim J., Kim S. W., Song W. J., Kang B. S. (2005) Analytical approach to bursting in tube hydroforming using diffuse plastic instability. *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 47 (7): 1023–1037.
- [22] Kim S.W., Song W. J., Kang B. S., Kim J. Bursting failure prediction in tube hydroforming using FLSD. *Int J Adv Manuf Technol* 2008, doi: 0.1007/s00170-008-1488-3 (in press).
- [23] Marciniak Z., Kuczynski K. (1967) Limit strains in the process of stretch-forming sheet metal. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*. 9: 609–20.
- [24] Zhao L., Sowerby R., Sklad M. P. (1996) A theoretical and experimental investigation of limit strain in sheet metal forming. *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 38 (12): 1307–1317.
- [25] Ganjiani M., Assempour A. (2007) An improved analytical approach for determination of forming limit diagrams considering the effects of yield functions, *J. Mater. Proc. Tech.* 182 (1-3): 598–607.
- [26] Assempour A., Safikhani A. R., Hashemi R. (2009) An improved strain gradient approach for determination of deformation localization and forming limit diagrams. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 209 (4): 1758-1769.

- [27] Safikhani A. R., Hashemi R., Assempour A. (2009) Some numerical aspects of necking solution in prediction of sheet metal forming limits by strain gradient plasticity. *J. Materials and Design*, 30 (3): 727-740.
- [28] Ahmadi S., Eivani A.R., Akbarzadeh A. (2008) An experimental and theoretical study on the prediction of forming limit diagrams using new BBC yield criteria and M–K analysis. *Comput. Mater. Sci.* Doi:10.1016/j.commatsci.2008.08.013 (in press).
- [29] Ganjiani M., Assempour A. (2007) Implementation of a robust algorithm for prediction of forming limit diagrams. *J. Mat. Engng Performance* 17(1):1-6.
- [30] Asnafi N., Skogsga°rdh A. (2000) Theoretical and experimental analysis of stroke-controlled tube Hydroforming. *Materials Science and Engineering A*, 279 (1-2): 95–110.
- [31] Press W.H., Teukolsky S.A., Vetterling W.T., Flannery B.P. (1992) *Numerical Recipes in Fortran 77: The art of scientific computing*, second edn., Chapter 9, Cambridge University Press.
- [32] Hill R. (1948) A theory of the yielding and plastic flow of anisotropic materials, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*; A193, 281-297.
- [33] Simha C.H.M., Gholipour J., Bardelcik A., Worswick M.J. (2007) Prediction of necking in tubular hydroforming using an extended stress-based flc. *ASME J Eng Mater Technol.* 129 (1):136–147.

Figure 1: Schematic of the M-K model

Figure 2: Input loading paths with five different cases [20].

Figure 3: Hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams for STKM-11A tube (a) FLDs
(b) FLS

Figure 4: Hydroforming strain and stress limit diagrams for DP600 (HG/Z140) (a)
FLDs (b) FLSDs

Figure 5: Model of one ring of the bellows (present work)

Figure 6: Loading conditions for experiments and FEM (present work)

Figure 7: (a) Hydroforming stress limit diagram and major and minor stress values
extracted from FEM for acceptable bellows (material: Phosphor Bronze CuSn6) (b)
manufactured bellows in safe region of the pressure (c) acceptable part from FEM
(present work)

Figure 8: (a) Hydroforming stress limit diagram and major and minor stress values
extracted from FEM (material: Phosphor Bronze CuSn6) (b) manufactured bellows in
safe region of the pressure (c) stress contours on the failure bellows (present work)

Figure 9: Hydroforming strain limit diagram and major and minor strain values
extracted from FEM for acceptable bellows (material: Phosphor Bronze CuSn6)
(present work)

Figure 10: Strain path of the element 428 (tube material: Phosphor Bronze CuSn6)

Table 1: Material properties of tube

Material	t (mm)	K (MPa)	n	r	ε_0
STKM-11A tube [20]	-	1400	0.17	2.14	0
DP600 (HG/Z140) [30]	1.47	988	0.182	1	0

Table.2. Mechanical properties and dimension of the initial tubes

Material properties						
Material	n	K (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	E (GPa)	ν	P (Kg/m ³)
CuSn6	0.233	635	386	92	0.34	8000
Dimensions(mm)						
r_0	t_0	D_c	d	Number of rings		
6.75	0.1	9	0.5	10		

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(a)

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